

Doing exercise during quarantine

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Abstract

The coronavirus pandemic has disturbed a vast variety of activities including doing exercise. Physical activities play a vital role in community health which is limited during this worldwide crisis. The pandemic not only disturbs physical activities but also affects mental health by increasing fear, stress, and depression. This manuscript presents a multipurpose home practice to compensate for both muscular and respiratory weakness due to the lack of exercise, and it also seeks to reduce the mental effects of pervasive illness by practicing yoga. Although their separate effect has been investigated for many years, simultaneous application of three methods needs to be considered. Since the result of each method is effective separately, a mix of these methods is highly beneficial to people who have a sedentary lifestyle during the quarantine.

Keywords: coronavirus; doing exercise; quarantine; yoga; home practice

1. Introduction

Coronavirus infectious, known as 2019-nCoV, was detected in Wuhan, China, on December 31, 2019, from personal exposure to a local seafood market, and now it is a global issue for many counties including Iran [1], [2]. Coronavirus leads to negative social and mental consequences [3] which was included unemployment. According to the Office for National Statistics (ONS), 1.62 million people lost their job over the previous three months [4]. Although all sectors of the world economy have been affected by the pandemic, some sectors like sport encounter a real crisis [5].

Many health organizations, including the National Health Commission of the People's Republic of China, the World Health Organization (WHO), and the US Centres for Disease Control and Prevention have enacted many laws and regulations to reduce and prevent the risks of corona outbreaks [6]. These restrictions disturb people's daily activity include exercise and physical activity. Since many governments and health organizations have prioritized the fight against the disease, they have paid less attention to sports activities. Increasing the duration of quarantine will have devastating consequences for obesity, muscle weakness, and inactivity, which are very important for professional athletes, especially those who engage in aerobic and endurance sports.

According to reports provided by the WHO, the coronavirus epidemic also causes fear, worry, and stress in people [7]. Therefore, in this manuscript, considering the possible negative consequences, a multipurpose home exercise including yoga, muscle, and breathing exercises for individuals and professional athletes is presented.

2. Practice

2.1. Respiratory practice

After the age of 20, the function of the lungs gradually becomes weaker and they can no longer hold the air inside them as before [8]. This is where breathing exercises can help you to strengthen your lungs so that you can increase the volume of your lungs and make them look like the first day. This kind of exercise also uses to clear mucus from the lungs after pneumonia of asthma and other respiratory diseases. The quarantine is a suitable time for athletics to increasing lung capacity by these practices. Some practices are mention here:

2.1.1. Diaphragmatic breathing (belly breathing)

The diaphragm is a dome-shaped muscle that plays a vital role in breathing. Strengthening this muscle has a significant effect on the quality of breathing. People can use diaphragmatic breathing to strengthen this muscle. Diaphragmatic breathing result in [9]:

- Strengthen the diaphragm
- Decrease the work of breathing by slowing your breathing rate
- Decrease oxygen demand
- Use less effort and energy to breathe

In order to practice lie on your back and put your hand on your body as shown in *figure 1 A*. breath slowly via your nose so that your stomach moves out *figure 1 B*. Tighten your stomach muscles, letting them fall inward as you exhale through pursed lips *figure 1 C*. to find more detail look at reference [9].

Figure 1. Steps of performing diaphragmatic breathing [9]

To find more detail look at reference [9].

2.1.2. Pursed-lips breathing

Pursed-lips breathing makes breathing slower and opening the airway for a longer time bring about a reduction in breathing work. This makes it easier for the lungs to function and improves the exchange of oxygen and carbon dioxide. This breathing exercise is far easier than diaphragmatic practice for the novice, and it is easy to perform. It can be practiced at any time [10].

2.2.3. Box Breathing

Box breathing, square breathing, is a technique used when taking slow, deep breaths. It can heighten performance and concentration while also used for reducing stress. It's also called four-square breathing. This technique can be beneficial to anyone, especially those who want to meditate or reduce stress to find out more about this or further practice look at the reference[11].

2.2. Muscle practice

Home exercise compensates for lack of activities during the quarantine. This form of exercise has different aspects include strengthening and stretching exercises or other some practice to improve balance and control, or a mix of all of them [6]. In this kind of exercise, the individual can use a home appliance or their body weight. Some of them are mentioned that need no equipment or large space, see table 1. To find more exercise according to your capability (beginner, intermediate, advanced) and to perform the exercises correctly look at reference [12].

Table 1. Home practices and their related organs or muscles

Practice	Related Organ or Muscle
Squat	Legs And Core
Bridge	Posterior Chain
Stationary Lunge	Quads And Hamstring
Pushup	Shoulder, Chest Muscle
Side-Lying Hip Abduction	Hip Muscle
Plank	Core Muscle
Dead Bug	Core Muscle
Hollow Hold To Jackknife	Core Muscle
High Knee Running In Place	Core, Legs
Triceps Dips	Triceps, Deltoid

2.3. Yoga

Yoga is an Indian ancient practice that is rooted in philosophy[13]. It has been known for its effects on controlling stress

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